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Evaluating the Effectiveness of 9th Grade English Textbooks in Uzbekistan: a Content Analysis

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Abstract: The quality of educational materials plays a crucial role in shaping students' learning experiences and outcomes. In Uzbekistan, the 9th grade English curriculum serves as a pivotal stage in language acquisition, preparing students for higher education and global communication. As the demand for proficient English speakers increases, it becomes essential to evaluate the effectiveness of the textbooks used in this critical phase of education.

Key words: education, experience, global communication

INTRODUCTION

This article presents a content analysis of 9th grade English textbooks in Uzbekistan, focusing on their alignment with educational standards, relevance to students' lives, and the development of essential language skills. By examining aspects such as cultural representation, pedagogical approaches, and the inclusion of contemporary topics, we aim to identify strengths and areas for improvement within these textbooks. The findings will contribute to ongoing discussions about educational reforms in Uzbekistan and provide insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers striving to enhance English language instruction. Through this evaluation, we seek to ensure that students are equipped with the necessary skills to thrive in an increasingly interconnected world.

The methodology for teaching foreign languages, particularly as a second foreign language, has gained significant attention in contemporary linguistics. This approach emphasizes the importance of incorporating the culture, customs, and traditions of the language being taught, utilizing relevant cultural insights for educational purposes. Numerous studies focus on innovative teaching methods in foreign language education, especially within the framework of the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), which outlines standards for language learning, teaching, and assessment.

In Uzbekistan, the educational system mandates that ninth-grade students achieve an A2 proficiency level in foreign languages by the end of their studies. The presidential decree from January 28, 2022, on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan, reinforces the need for reforms across all educational stages, aiming to provide modern learning opportunities that meet international standards. A key focus is on fostering students' abilities to think in a foreign language, articulate their thoughts, and develop their intellectual potential, thereby enhancing their overall readiness for communication in diverse contexts.

The primary objective of foreign language instruction in Uzbekistan is to cultivate communicative competence, enabling students to engage effectively in everyday, academic, and professional environments within a multicultural setting. Communicative competence encompasses various sub-competencies, including linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, and discourse competencies.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the formation of communicative competence in a foreign language in order to carry out activities in everyday, scientific and professional fields in a multicultural world.

Foreign language communicative competence is the ability to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the foreign language in the process of communication. A few more competencies can be defined below, as they are also closely related to communicative competence:

Sociolinguistic competence makes it possible to choose the necessary linguistic form and expression method based on a speech situation, communicative goal and desire of the speaker. Sociolinguistic competence includes socio-cultural competence and shows the ability to present national characteristics of authentic speech: knowledge of customs, values, rituals and other national-cultural characteristics of the country where one lives and compares it with the country where the language is studied. holds;

Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to get out of difficult situations by repeatedly asking, apologizing, etc. In this standard, discourse competence was included in pragmatic competence. This competence involves expressing thoughts in oral or written speech using appropriate language tools;

Discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals in order to ensure consistency in oral or written speech.

Linguistic competence involves knowledge of language fundamentals such as phonetics, vocabulary, and grammar, along with skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

The requirements for the knowledge and skills attained by graduating students in foreign languages are

aligned with educational content across all levels of education in Uzbekistan. These requirements are articulated using a "can do" framework, supplemented by necessary grammar, vocabulary, and phonetic components to ensure clarity and accessibility. Furthermore, the curriculum emphasizes the integration of assessment criteria for state certification, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of graduates' foreign language proficiency.

All levels of education in the country should be considered in the development of evaluation criteria for the state certification of graduates. The main document containing the level of students' knowledge of foreign languages and the requirements for their training, as well as recommendations for teaching them foreign languages, is the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the state education standard for foreign languages of the continuous education system This document is approved by the decision No. 124 of May 8, 2013 and contains the following sections:

1. general rules;
2. structure of the state education standard;
3. goals and tasks of educational science;
4. educational content;
5. requirements for the levels of knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by graduates.

The state educational standards, established by the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan in 2013, outline the expectations for foreign language instruction across the continuous education system. These standards encompass general provisions, educational objectives, content requirements, and specified competencies for students. The alignment of these standards with the CEFR framework ensures that ninth-grade graduates are equipped to achieve an A2 proficiency level, with particular attention to the distinct needs of students in specialized language programs.

The curriculum emphasizes the development of writing skills as a critical component of communicative competence. For ninth-grade students, expected writing tasks include composing personal letters, filling out forms with personal information, and producing simple narratives. The curriculum prioritizes productive and reproductive activities that encourage creative expression while also focusing on the writing process itself.

At the A2 level, students should be capable of writing brief messages and personal letters, completing forms, and crafting simple biographies. These writing tasks reflect three psychological dimensions: motivational, exploratory, and executional. Although the concept of writing skills is not fully articulated within the standards, the demand for enhanced written communication competencies is increasingly recognized, particularly in the context of a rapidly evolving information landscape.

The ninth-grade English curriculum includes three hours of instruction per week, totaling 102 hours annually. Under the guidance of Professor J.J. Jalolov, the curriculum delineates specific competencies aligned with state standards. The division of proficiency levels across grades caters to the developmental characteristics of students.

Prof. J.J. In the foreign language curriculum for grades 1-9 developed in 2017 by the team of authors

under the leadership of Jalolov, the requirements for each competency given in the State Education Standard are listed in more detail. Here, the A2 level of knowledge of a foreign language is formed in the form of A2/1 level in 5-6 grades, A2/2 level in 7-8 grades, and A2/3 level in 9th grade. This division is made appropriately and corresponds to the psychological characteristics of the students depending on their age. Below are the requirements for written speech competence of the A2 level given in the curriculum for the ninth grade: 1) by types of educational activities; 2) a table classified by types of developing speech and language competences is given.

Requirements for foreign language written speech competence in the foreign language curriculum for the ninth grade

Continuing education class and corresponding CEFR level	Competence	Types of activities (according to the type of activity)	
		Productive	Reproductive
9 (A2/3)	Lexical competence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - write a dictation and a statement on a given topic and on a free topic; - checking the written work, correcting errors; - to write a brief summary of the contents of the text read and mastered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - write a statement or an essay on the topics presented in the textbook - writing an abbreviated text plan for oral presentation of the read or heard text; - written clarification of the content of the prepared plan or theses; - correctly form the text of (informal) letters, e-mails, SMS, notes, news, reports, articles and diaries; - write short news and personal letters using everyday words; - creating a text expressing personal opinion and making a conclusion.
	Grammatical competence	not available	not available

In summary, while the curriculum for ninth-grade English provides a framework for developing writing skills, it does not adequately address the broader concept of written communication as a separate competency. Given the increasing prevalence of written communication in modern contexts, particularly in light of recent

global shifts towards remote work and education, it is crucial to refine the focus on written speech competence in foreign language education. The integration of innovative pedagogical techniques, such as fostering critical thinking through writing, can enhance the effectiveness of teaching written communication skills within the curriculum.

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